

INTERPRETATION OF ARTISTIC IMAGES IN ISAJON SULTON'S NOVEL "OZOD"

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6997493>

Abstract. *In this article, the novel of "Ozod" by the novelist of new period Isajon Sulton is poetically observed, the main idea and oriental traditions are discussed in the work. The originality of the artistic symbols in the novel is interpreted as having a symbolic figurative meaning.*

Keywords: *symbol, symbolic images, artistic representations of road and wind.*

ИНТЕРПРЕТАЦИЯ ХУДОЖЕСТВЕННЫХ ОБРАЗОВ В РОМАНЕ ИСАДЖОНА СУЛТОН «ОЗОД»

Аннотация. *В данной статье поэтически рассматривается роман «Озод» писателя нового периода Исаджона Султон, обсуждаются основная идея и восточные традиции в произведении. Своеобразие художественных символов в романе трактуется как имеющее символическое образное значение.*

Ключевые слова: *символ, символические образы, художественные изображения дороги и ветра.*

INTRODUCTION

Fiction, which is the art of speech, like other arts, reflects life through the spiritual experiences, thoughts, activities, struggles, and emotions of the people in it. It should be noted that the main subject of fiction is man. In short, the image of man is central to the science of literature. The society in which he lives and the processes that take place in him, such as nature and the social environment, are used to show the peculiarities of the human person, to reflect his nature more vividly. So what is an emblem?

MATERIALS AND METHODS

"An emblem is an image, an appearance, as well as a sign, a symbol embodied in the eyes in the imagination." [1]

In fiction, the symbol is used as a synonym for "image." That is why the concept of artistic symbolism is often used instead of artistic image.

During the years of independence, Uzbek literature has also undergone a process of "renewal", especially in the epic round. In particular, our novel is about the analysis of human dreams, intimate experiences, the human psyche. Isajon Sulton's novel "Ozod" is one of the epic works created during the independence period, the puzzle of personality is widely observed, consisting of a collection of figurative signs and symbols. The novel "Ozod" is a work written in a completely new spirit. The author has moved away from the traditional plot, the image of traditional images in the novel. We can say that this is a complete philosophical work. The composition of the work is built in such a way that all the artistic symbols unite around Ozod, who is looking for the tulip-happiness of his destiny. Ozod is a symbol of thinking that seeks to know the mysteries of the universe and moves towards its own destiny. Along the way, he encounters various reflections and their experiences of destiny. But the answers to the age-old questions they have posed to the outside world are new. In the person of the protagonist, we see a free man who thinks and observes independently on the basis of signs and details, and whose inner need for self-study calls him to even higher levels. As literary scholar Abdugafur Rasulov

puts it, "In fact, I am in favor of thinking that all the characters in the novel are Ozod himself. Isn't that the same logic when it comes to reflections. If he set out on a journey of meaning, would he be like his father and spend the day working in the fields? If he aspired to wealth, would his destiny be like wandering in the paths of remorse and regret, like the fate of the owner of the vineyard? All the young men who are growing up are Saints. Ozod aspired to Dilorom, who was a peacemaker because of his sainthood nature. Yes, the woman is Dilorom, but the homeland is also Dilorom." [2]

RESULTS

In the person of "Ozod" the writer conditionally injects proportion to the main idea of Farididdin Attor's "Mantiq ut-tayr", Alisher Navoi's "Lison ut-tayr", Jalaliddin Rumi's "Ichindagi ichingdadur" [3]

At the heart of it all is the idea of self, of the universe, of man. Sa'dulla Quronov thinks: "The novel "Ozod" is artistically and figuratively connected with the literature of the East. After all, the plot of the work is close to the plot of F. Attor's "Mantiq ut-tayr" and Alisher Navoi's "Lison ut-tayr". In "Mantiq ut-tayr", birds in search of Semurg cross seven valleys. These valleys are a symbol of the seven stages that lead to the truth in mysticism. "In the novel "Ozod", Ozod travels in search of the mysterious tulip that brings happiness and bliss." [4]

"The road is clear: if you cross the Uchyongak, there is the Salt Desert and the Aydinkol Lake. Farther away from Aydinkol there is a flat desert, and behind the desert there are rocks. Then the mountain and the rock begin, and farther inland, between the two mountains, the slippery high cliffs rise to the top of those cliffs." [5]

Continuing the classical traditions of the East, the author focuses on the image of the road. It should be noted that the location sought in the play does not matter, the most important is the path traversed by the protagonist. Because that's what leads him to the pinnacle of enlightenment, the lesson of life:

"You also asked about the road," said the Master. They said: "So-and-so set off and went to so-and-so's place." Behind this statement are the landscapes of the roads, the nature, the images, the words and attitudes of different people, the mountains and the gardens, the rivers and the streams, the deserts and other big and small things that lead in different directions. There are trails, villages and cities, night and day, wonders and dangers. It's like a window that says "So-and-so" has set off and gone to so-and-so's place, and if you look at it, you can see what I'm saying behind it. The window is visible, the inside is behind. The result is obvious when he reaches his destination. In fact, all of this is the opposite. That person's goal is to get to the destination." [6]

Indeed, these same views are a fact of life. In fact, everyone has a long way to go from birth to death. But the interesting thing is that the destination of a human being depends on how he travels this path of life. This idea, like the image of the owner of the vineyard in the play, encourages a person to look back and summarize his life as he grows older:

"Will you then begin to hear the voices of your past? The paths, the rocks, the ravines, the cliffs of your many years of life ... you begin to see events unfold like bushes growing in their bosoms. Then you think about your life, because life has blown over this corner like the wind. You too will be swept away by the wind." [7]

And through the image of the blind man in the work, we can see that the eyes of the human heart are open. Although the human eye cannot see around, it understands the whole

world more deeply than the naked eye through its heart and mind. Man also expresses the power of things in life that he does not pay attention to:

"Everything that lies here is a word, my boy," said the blind man calmly. "Everything you see around you is a word. You know, the beginning and the end of the human being are words and meanings. Have you heard that the world is completely the opposite? That's the decent thing to do, and it should end there. Because one day the universe will disappear completely, and only the words spoken and their meanings will remain. From them new worlds will be built." [8]

DISCUSSION

This emblem played a very important role in the plot of the work. Because in the spiritual growth of Ozod, the wisdom spoken by this sage serves as a guide for him. If we pay attention to the wisdom he narrates, we will feel from the bottom of our hearts how influential and at the same time they are true.

The wind is the symbol that accompanies Ozod until he reaches his destination. Ozod observes the "philosophy of reflections" because of him. In fact, the image of the wind is portrayed as a prophet, a narrator of all the events in the novel.

The author uses a lot of puzzles in the play. But under each puzzle there is a truth that humanity aspires to. The closer you get to each destination, the closer you get to the pinnacle of enlightenment. Finally, he realizes himself. He will know the secrets of the universe.

CONCLUSIONS

To come to the conclusion, Isajon Sulton's novel "Ozod" seems to have been created in response to eternal riddles. The more one reads this philosophical work, the more one realizes the wonders of the world around him, as well as his inner world. The author's goal through the work is to purify the soul, to introduce oneself. In fact, the artistic symbols used in their place, which contain many meanings, are really important in this. After all, in understanding and interpreting the essence of the work, it is very important to know the place of the symbols in the plot, to get to the root of them.

REFERENCES

1. O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati. T.: "O'zbekiston milliy ensiklopediyasi" Davlat ilmiy nashriyoti, 2006-2008. 485-bet.
2. Rasulov A. Akslar falsafasi. –T.: "Sharq", 2012.- 420-bet.
3. Toliboyev X. Poetik mushohadada ramziylik // Sharq yulduzi. Toshkent. 2016. №11
4. Quronov S. Isajon Sultonning ikki romani haqida. www.kh-davron.uz.
5. I. Sulton. Ozod.-T.: "Sharq", 2012.
6. Ахмедова Ш. Ўзбек адабий танқидчилиги жанрлари. Тошкент. 2008.134 б.
7. Akhmedova Sh., Qahramonov Q. The happiness of true science. Tashkent. "Navruz" .2015.
8. Akhmedova Sh. N. PROGRESS OF PORTRAIT WRITING IN THE PERIOD OF GLOBALIZATION IN LITERARY STUDIES // Russia-Uzbekistan. International educational and socio-cultural technologies: vectors of development. - 2019. - S. 12-14.
9. Akhmedova Sh. N., Norova N. ABOUT DEVELOPMENT AND CHARACTER OF THE GENRE OF REVIEW // International scientific journal. - 2016. -- P. 37.
10. Axmedova Sh. N. DEVELOPMENT OF PORTRAITS IN UZBEK AND FRENCH LITERATURE // International Journal of Word Art. - 2020. - T. 6. - №3.

11. Davronova S. EASTERN AND WESTERN LITERARY TRADITION IN THE MODERN UZBEK NOVELS //World science. – 2016. – Т. 4. – №. 5 (9). 32. Sharipova L. Literary yor-yor //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State
12. Муродов Г. Н. Литературно-художественная общность романов Абдулла Кадири //Вестник Южно-Уральского государственного гуманитарно-педагогического университета. – 2012. – №. 2.
13. Назаров Б, Расулов А.,Ахмедова Ш.,Қаҳрамонов Қ. Ўзбек адабий танқиди тарихи. Тошкент. “Тафаккур қаноти”. 2012. 354 б.
14. Nasima Saidburxonovna Qodirova, “THE ANALYSIS OF IBRAHIM HAKKULOV IN NEW UZBEK LITERATURE”, IEJRD - International Multidisciplinary Journal, vol. 6, no. TITFL, pp. 152-157, Apr. 2021.
15. Norova N. B. CREATIVE ABILITIES OF THE ARTIST IN THE APPLICATION OF THE ART (ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE LYRICS OF OSMAN KOCHKAR) //Scientific reports of Bukhara State University. – 2020. – Т. 4. – №. 5. – С. 214-221.
16. Saidburhonovna K. N., Ne'matovna A. S. Style and skill: Critic’s artistic ability //International Journal of Innovative Technology and Exploring Engineering. – 2019. – Т. 8. – №. 9 S3. – С. 1245-1250.
17. Safarova H. “HAPPINESS IS THE FLAG LANGUAGE, FROM HAPPINESS I AM ALSO A TONGUE!”... ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE WORK OF THE POET SAMANDAR VOHIDOV //Конференции. – 2020. 29.
18. Qodirova N. S. SOME CHARACTERISTIC FEATURES, SKILLS AND STYLE OF THE LITERARY CRITIC //Web of Scholar. – 2018. – Т. 5. – №. 2. – С. 32-35.
19. Kadirova N. S. CRITICAL STYLE AND GENRE DIVERSITY //Theoretical & Applied Science. – 2020. – №. 4. – С. 428-433. 30.
20. Khudoykulova M. A. THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE CONTROVERSIAL ARTICLE GENRE IN THE 20 YEARS OF XX CENTURY //Scientific reports of Bukhara State University. – 2020. – Т. 4. – №. 1. – С. 231-237.
21. Sharipova L. Literary yor-yor //Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University. – 2019. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 218-222.
22. Usmonova, D. S., & Yusupova, M. I. Q. (2021). Comparative analysis of the somatic phraseological units of the english and russian languages with the component “heart”. *Current research journal of philological sciences* (2767-3758), 2(11), 94-99.
23. Усмонова Д. С. Роль и особенность соматических фразеологизмов различных языков //Мировая наука. – 2019. – №. 9. – С. 250-252.
24. Satvoldievna, U. D., & Qizi, R. K. B. (2020). Linguistic analysis of puns in the English language. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (2 (147)), 38-40.
25. Satvoldievna, U. D., & Qizi, A. M. N. (2020). Comparative typological analysis of semantic-structural features of conditional inclination in different systematic languages. *Проблемы современной науки и образования*, (4-2 (149)), 21-23.
26. Усмонова Д. С. Роль и особенность соматических фразеологизмов различных языков //Мировая наука. – 2019. – №. 9. – С. 250-252.
27. Usmanova, D. ., & Shodieva, G. N. (2022). ISSUES OF CLASSIFICATION OF WORD CATAGORIES IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE. *Academic Research in Educational Sciences*, 3(6), 1276–1280.

28. qizi Shodieva, G. N., & Dusmatov, H. H. (2022, July). RINCIPILES OF DIVISION OF WORD CATAGORIES IN UZBEK LANGUAGE. In *INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCES ON LEARNING AND TEACHING* (Vol. 1, No. 11, pp. 38-43).